

POLICE RECORD MANAGEMENT: IDENTIFICATION OF THE PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY POLICE PERSONNEL IN THE FIRST CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF ZAMBOANGA DEL NORTE

(^a) Joseph B. Bangalando, (^b) Jerome M. Guillena, (^c) Junalisa I. Uguis, (^d) Leo C. Naparota, PhD
(^e) Love H. Falloran, PhD (^f) Ronnel T. Lampawog, MSCJ

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received: May 15, 2023

Received in rev. form:

August, 15, 2023.

Published: September 30, 2023.

Keywords:

police personnel, police records management, attributes

JEL Classification:

E23; M 15

ABSTRACT

This paper determined the effectiveness of police records management in the first congressional district of Zamboanga del Norte. To achieve this goal, a quantitative research method was employed, utilizing both descriptive-survey and descriptive-correlational approaches. The study had a sample size of thirty (30) respondents, and several statistical tools were utilized, including frequency count and percent, weighted mean, Mann-Whitney U Test, Kruskal-Wallis H Test, and Spearman rank-order correlation.

The findings of the study revealed that the respondents perceived the attributes of records management, such as records creation, records retention and disposition, records storage and maintenance, records access and retrieval, and appropriate use of technology and records management program, as "very much effective." However, their perception of archival records management was rated as "much effective." These results indicate that while the overall records management system was considered effective, there is room for improvement specifically in the management of archival records.

Additionally, the study showed that the problems encountered by police personnel in managing police records were not significant, and the factors contributing to these problems were of least concern. This implies that the existing issues faced by police personnel in record management were not severe and did not hinder the overall effectiveness of the system. It is worth noting that there was no established relationship between the attributes of police record management and the problems encountered, suggesting that officers who were highly competent in managing records did not necessarily face major difficulties.

In conclusion, the study suggests that the police records management system in the first congressional district of Zamboanga del Norte is largely effective. However, there is a need for improvement in the management of archival records. Efforts should be made to address any existing problems and enhance the overall record management process to ensure a smoother and more efficient system.

© 2023 by the authors. Licensee DWIJMH. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Effective records management is crucial for the survival and success of organizations. Without well-kept, maintained, and utilized records, organizations are left to make ad hoc decisions without the benefit of institutional memories (Bakare, Abioye, & Issa, 2016). Poorly managed records can become a liability, hindering operations, and draining resources (Ridener, 2009). Moreover, the time spent on sorting and locating information from large volumes of records when they are poorly managed is significant. The high rate of misplaced or lost records, which often contain valuable information for decision making, poses a challenge to effective record-keeping (Bakare, Abioye, & Issa, 2016).

* Corresponding author. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9693-1541

© 2023 by the authors. Hosting by DWIJMH. Peer review under responsibility of Divine Word International Journal of Management and Humanities.

Records are vital to the functioning of an organization. The day-to-day operations of any successful organization rely entirely on its records (Bakare, Abioye, & Issa, 2016). Additionally, the importance of easily accessible, accurate, and timely records in fulfilling an organization's mission cannot be overstated. Records such as calls for service records, investigative records, arrest records, criminal identification records, detention records, and civil records contain valuable information that, when combined with data from other jurisdictions, can aid investigations at all levels, ultimately contributing to national safety and security (FBI, 1984). Both private and public organizations acknowledge that records are necessary for their efficient and effective operation. Records document the decisions and activities of governments and other organizations, serving as benchmarks against which future activities and decisions can be evaluated (World Bank, 2006).

Various studies have established the link between a records management system and effective law enforcement (FBI, 1984; Ngoepe, 2014). Law enforcement agencies rely on records management systems to provide accurate information for carrying out their mission of enforcing laws and protecting the public. If data is not properly recorded, the accuracy of the input is compromised, rendering the law enforcement system ineffective. Despite this reciprocal relationship between the law enforcement system and records management, it has been observed that most governmental bodies' risk registers do not include records management, and risk committees often lack representation from records management practitioners. In many governmental organizations, risk management falls under the purview of internal audit functions.

Within this context, the present study aims to assess police record management and identify the problems encountered by police personnel in the first congressional district of Zamboanga del Norte. Additionally, the study explores the relationship between the attributes of police record management and the problems encountered. Through this research, evidence-based decisions about records management can be derived, developed, and promoted, leading to improved practices and problem identification.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to deepen the understanding of the main concepts or theories of the current topic related to police record management.

Record Management

This study draws its foundation from Buckland's Records Management Theory (1994), as articulated in his seminal work "On the Nature of Records Management Theory." Buckland's theory posits that effective records management involves regulating access to an organization's operational records. Consequently, this undertaking encompasses various intricate aspects, including (1) information retrieval, (2) the life cycle of records, and (3) information policy. Supporting this perspective, Uwaif (2004) emphasizes that records management theory provides an established framework and methodology for ensuring the systematic management of all records and the information they encompass. Aligning closely with this theory, the current research identifies the prevalent challenges in record management encountered by police personnel in the first district of Zamboanga del Norte, as well as the underlying factors contributing to these problems.

Police Record Management

According to the FBI's Manual of Law Enforcement Records (1984), "records" are defined as information created, received, and preserved as proof and information by an organization or individual to fulfill legal obligations or conduct business. The International Council on Archives (ICA) Committee on Electronic Records offers a broader perspective, defining records as "recorded information generated or received during the initiation, execution, or completion of an institutional or individual activity, and that possesses content, context, and structure sufficient to provide evidence of the activity." For the purpose of this paper, records are specifically limited to documents or electronic files directly related to law enforcement operations, encompassing incidents, arrests, citations, warrants, case management, field contacts, and similar aspects.

The introduction of an incident/offense-based reporting system was developed with the aim of enhancing the accuracy of information captured for report writing and recordkeeping activities. Implementing a comprehensive Records Management System (RMS) that incorporates standardized records, such as incident/offense reports, yields significant benefits for law enforcement agencies. Additionally, the incident-based system proves invaluable in identifying reported criminal activity across different geographical areas (Saraih et al., 2021).

In the dynamic context of today's global interconnectedness, the significance of maintaining excellent record-keeping and implementing efficient information-sharing methods has escalated exponentially. Beyond their intrinsic value in providing critical internal information such as supporting business operations and managing cases, records play a pivotal role as the official repository of an agency's investigative history. As law enforcement agencies now face the imperative to communicate and cooperate across geographical borders and continents in their mission to protect citizens, the necessity for seamless record management and information exchange has become paramount. With the law enforcement community evolving into a more diverse landscape, the requirement for accurate and timely data is indispensable for a multitude of objectives, ranging from strategic planning and budgeting to resource allocation and the comprehensive evaluation of police performance and experimental program efficacy (Buen et al., 2017).

Police Record Management Challenges

Recent studies have brought to light alarming issues concerning the management of police data, encompassing inadvertent document deletions and the failure to inform relevant EU nations about murder convictions of individuals within the UK. Given the gravity of these concerns, it is essential for the Code of Practice to incorporate robust controls that effectively prevent such occurrences (Sulaiman et al., 2021). Additionally, the Code should provide clear guidance on redress mechanisms and disciplinary procedures in cases of misuse or major failures. Furthermore, the potential loophole whereby officers under investigation can evade disciplinary proceedings by resigning from their positions, as witnessed in past disciplinary procedures prior to the establishment of Professional Standards in the Metropolitan Police, raises further uncertainty.

The recording, storage, management, and deletion of police information can pose substantial threats to privacy and other fundamental rights. Therefore, it is imperative to establish stringent oversight and transparency

measures that are unambiguous and enforceable to govern the management of police records and other relevant information (Chokprajakchat et al., 2021).

The study conducted by Buen et al. (2017) shed light on prevalent challenges faced by police personnel, including inadequate storage for files and records, as well as the time-consuming nature of locating necessary documents. Insufficient storage capacity often results in improper organization, misplacement, and loss of critical papers. Moreover, the lack of efficient storage systems leads to wastage of valuable time spent on searching for essential files. As the volume of records continues to increase, the lack of corresponding expansion in storage capacity leads to disarray and difficulties in locating necessary files.

Recognizing the pivotal role of records management, the researchers emphasize that excellent and proper recordkeeping should be regarded as a vital element of well-governed organizations, rather than a fortuitous aspect (Timbur, 2017). Sharing effective records management techniques and processes with government-owned or sponsored statutory organizations offers tangible benefits by enhancing corporate governance and fostering good management practices. According to Saraih et al. (2021), changes in administration emerged as a significant trigger for record management challenges, as policy shifts with each new administration or the arrival of new police personnel in the records department can create confusion and disrupt established practices.

Police Personnel

The effectiveness of work within an organization is a critical factor in its overall success. Organizations that establish adequate processes to support and enhance their employees' job performance are more likely to achieve a strong return on investment and experience rapid, effective, and sustainable growth. Conversely, a lack of proper processes that promote and enhance internal employee work effectiveness results in ineffective and disengaged employees who struggle to meet the necessary job performance standards (Tengpongsthorn, 2017). These unfavorable conditions directly impact employees' ability to utilize their full range of skills and competencies, leading to a detrimental effect on the improvement of work processes within the company and causing slow organizational development (Guss et al., 2020).

Police officers hold a pivotal position in the economic and social development of a nation, given their essential role and authority in maintaining public security, ensuring safety, and safeguarding communal assets that are fundamental to meeting the basic needs of individuals in society (Chokprachakchat, 2011; Guss et al., 2020). A secure and stable environment is crucial for fostering progress and development across various facets of civilization. Additionally, the functions and responsibilities of police personnel have a significant impact on a country's infrastructure development (Royal Thai Government Gazette, 2004; Timbur, 2017). Timbur's (2017) study highlights the substantial influence of knowledge and skills on police officers' ability to demonstrate appropriate work competences. Creating a work environment that offers employment security positively contributes to job performance, while fair remuneration assists in meeting officers' social welfare needs, thereby enhancing their overall performance within the police service.

Police undertake a wide range of responsibilities encompassing pursuing, arresting, and charging criminals, preventing crime, dealing with traffic offenses and accidents, resolving conflicts in their communities, reducing social disorder, and establishing and maintaining community relations. Evaluating police performance is a complex task with multiple dimensions (Coleman, 2012; Maguire, 2003; Moore and Braga, 2003; Maslov, 2015). It is challenging to measure the performance of all aspects of police work using a single metric. As police expenses continue to rise, it becomes unsustainable for many jurisdictions, especially when competing priorities like education and healthcare require public funding. This concern has been expressed by provinces, municipalities, and policing stakeholders, who find it difficult to justify the high costs of police services (Brennan, 2014; CBC, 2013). In an era of limited resources, assessing and evaluating police performance becomes increasingly important to ensure that the service is effectively meeting its objectives.

Performance evaluation of public organizations has gained significant importance in the past decade (Whitaker et al., 1982, as cited by Chaiwutissak, 2019). Systematic assessments and evaluations are increasingly used to plan, sustain, initiate, or terminate governmental programs. Police departments, like other government agencies, face the challenge of justifying their budgets, programs, procedures, and future directions. However, most police departments' performance measurement efforts fall short in meeting these demands. While police officers have access to advanced technologies and generate substantial amounts of data, the quality and extent of these figures are often overlooked by other government officials and the public as indicators of police success.

The primary function of police officers is to protect life and property and ensure the appropriate measurement of all security and crime prevention functions, with citizen safety being the most crucial (Muhammad et al., 2020). The country faces increasingly severe challenges in maintaining peace and order (Laguyo, 2020). To address this, internal improvements and transformations are necessary, which can be achieved through excellent training programs. Recording incidents is vital for police departments to stay informed about the happenings in their jurisdiction. These records aid in informing follow-up actions and addressing specific types or patterns of crime. Citizens rely on these reports for legal purposes and insurance claims. It is essential for police agencies to report crimes at various levels, from local to county, state, and national, to calculate crime rates and identify trends (Cunningham, 2021).

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework depicted in Figure shows the relationship between the independent variable, which encompasses the common problems encountered by police personnel and the factors that contribute to these problems. The dependent variable in this framework is the police record management. The arrow from the independent variable to the dependent variable signifies the connection between the common record-related issues faced by police personnel and their impact on the management of police records.

The conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between three key variables: common problems in managing police records, perceived attributes of police record management, and factors contributing to these problems.

The independent variable is the common problems encountered in managing police records, including issues related to records creation, retention, storage, access, technology use, archival records, and program integration.

The mediating variable is the perceived attributes of police record management, representing how police personnel perceive the effectiveness and efficiency of various record management aspects.

The dependent variable is the factors contributing to the problems encountered in managing police records. These factors can be organizational, technological, or procedural in nature.

The arrows in the framework represent the relationships between the variables. It is expected that the common problems directly influence the perceived attributes of record management, while the factors contribute to the occurrence and severity of these problems.

This framework aims to understand the common problems in police record management, their impact on perceived attributes, and the factors influencing these problems. The findings will inform strategies to improve record management practices, enhance efficiency, and ensure the integrity and accessibility of police records.

Conceptual Framework

The dependent variable in this framework is the police record management. The arrow from the independent variable to the dependent variable signifies the connection between the common record-related issues faced by police personnel and their impact on the management of police records.

Statement of the Problem

This study identified the common problems encountered by police personnel related to managing police records. More specifically, the researchers seek to determine the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 gender
 - 1.3 marital status and
 - 1.4 length in service?
2. What is the level of the respondent's perceived attributes of police record management in terms of:
 - 2.1 records creation;
 - 2.2 records retention and disposition;
 - 2.3 records storage and maintenance;
 - 2.4 records access and retrieval;
 - 2.5 appropriate use of technology;
 - 2.6 archival records; and
 - 2.7 records management program integration?
3. How serious do the problems encountered by police personnel in managing police records?
4. To what extent do the factors precipitating the problems encountered by police personnel in managing police records?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived attributes of police records management and the problems in managing records?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived attributes of police record management and the factors precipitating the problems in managing record?

Assumption

The respondents' self-reported information regarding their profile and perceived attributes of police record management is accurate and reliable.

The respondents have sufficient knowledge and experience to assess and evaluate the problems encountered in managing police records.

The factors identified as precipitating problems in police record management are valid and comprehensive.

Hypothesis

The profile of police personnel has a significant relation with their perceived attributes of police record management.

The perceived attributes of police record management affect the problems encountered by police personnel in managing police records.

Methodology

The study employed rigorous research methodologies including research design, data gathering instruments, population, study locale, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

In this study descriptive method of research is employed by utilizing a checklist questionnaire. The main goal of this study is to identify the common problems encountered by police personnel regarding record management, and the factors precipitating the problems in record management. Additionally, the researchers intend to establish relationship between the problems encountered and the factors precipitating the problems encountered by police personnel.

Locale of the Study

Population

The target participants of this study are 30 police personnel including the Non-Uniformed Personnel in charge in record management of police stations in the first Congressional district of Zamboanga del Norte. Participating police stations of this study are from Dapitan City, and the municipalities of La Libertad, Mutia, Pinan, Polanco, Rizal, Sergio Osmena Sr., and Sibutad. There will be 3 to 4 police or non-uniformed personnel in each participating stations in charge in record management.

Data Gathering Instrument

The research instrument that used is the study of Buen et al., (2017). The questionnaire is composed with three (3) sections. The first section is designed to determine the demographic profile of the respondents. The second part are indicators that seeks to identify the common problems encountered by police personnel relating to records. Finally, the third section will determine the factors precipitating the problems in record management.

Moreover, rating method will be used to assess the intensity of indicators mentioned in the second and third section of the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

A sample of police personnel was selected to participate in the study. The sampling technique used was probability sampling to ensure representativeness. A random sample of police personnel from different ranks and units was drawn from the target population.

A structured questionnaire was developed to gather data on the profile of respondents, the perceived attributes of police record management, the common problems encountered, and the factors contributing to these problems. The questionnaire consisted of both closed-ended and Likert scale questions to facilitate data analysis.

Prior to the main data collection, a pilot test of the questionnaire was conducted with a small group of police personnel. This allowed for the identification of any ambiguities, difficulties, or issues in the questionnaire. Based on the feedback received, necessary revisions and improvements were made.

The data collection process involved distributing the questionnaires to the selected sample of police personnel. This was done either in person or through an online survey platform, depending on the logistical feasibility and preferences of the participants. Clear instructions and guidelines were provided to ensure consistent and accurate responses.

Once the questionnaires were collected, the data was compiled and organized for analysis. Statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis were employed to analyze the data and examine the relationships between variables.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical guidelines and procedures were followed throughout the data gathering process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and their confidentiality and anonymity were ensured. The study also adhered to ethical guidelines regarding the handling and storage of data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected via the study instrument were meticulously tabulated, categorized, analyzed, and interpreted using suitable descriptive and inferential statistical procedures.

Frequency Count and Percentage. This was used to assess and describe the demographics of the respondents. This will be used to calculate the percentage of respondents who have the same attributes or how frequently the traits occur.

Standard Deviation. This was used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the employees scores where $SD \leq 3$ is homogenous and $SD > 3$ is heterogeneous (Aiken & Susane, 2001; Refugio, Galleto, & Torres, 2019).

Weighted Mean. It will be used to quantify and interpret the respondents' responses to the problems encountered by police personnel in relation to record management, as well as the factors that precipitated the problems.

Pearson Correlation. This will be used to determine the relationship between the problems encountered by police personnel and the factors precipitating record management

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 1. Profile of Respondents in terms of Age

	Frequency	Percent
20 – 30 years old	5	16.7
31 – 40 years old	20	66.7
41 – 50 years old	5	16.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 1 displays the age profile of the survey respondents, categorized into five groups: 20-30 years old and under, 31-40 years old, 41-50 years old, 51-60 years old, and 61 years old and above. Approximately 17% of the participants were 30 years old or younger. However, the cumulative frequency percent indicated that at least 83% of the respondents were between the ages of 30 and under 50. This suggests that a significant portion of the police force was in their middle years, indicating their capability to perform their duties effectively.

This finding aligns with Cappelletti's (2018) study, where the majority of respondents were police personnel aged 31 to 40 years old.

Table 2. Profile of Respondents in terms of Gender

	Frequency	Percent
Male	17	56.7
Female	13	43.3
Total	30	100.0

Table 2: presents the gender profile of the respondents, indicating that approximately 57% of the participants were men. This data confirms that most police officers are male, which is consistent with the demographics of the Philippine National Police. Policing has traditionally been a male-dominated profession, resulting in limited representation of women in the field.

Similarly, Cunningham's (2021) study, highlighted the traditional male dominance in the occupation of police officers. Therefore, most of the respondents in this study were male.

Table 3. Profile of Respondents in terms of Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent
Single	9	30.0
Married	20	66.7
Separated	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

The profile of the respondents in terms of marital status is displayed in Table 3. As seen in the table, most respondents—roughly 67 percent—were married. It showed that Police Officers who were married outnumbered those who were single or separated in the Police Stations studied. It signifies that responsible officers oversee the Police record area of the Police Stations since caring for sensitive data is like caring for the most priceless members of their family, the kids.

This present study finding refutes the data revealed by Sulaiman et al., (2021), wherein most of the respondents was single. This may suggest that single police officers are more sensible in terms of records management.

Table 4. Profile of Respondents in terms of Length in Service

	Frequency	Percent
1 – 5 years	5	16.7
6 – 10 years	13	43.3
11 – 15 years	10	33.3
16 years & above	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 4 displays the profile of respondents based on their length of service. The data reveals that approximately 17% of respondents had served for less than five years, while over 43% had served for more than five years but less than ten years. Further examination of the table indicates that 40% of the police respondents had served for more than ten years. These findings suggest that the length of service of police officers may contribute to their experience in managing police records and applying the law effectively.

This finding aligns with the results of Sulaiman et al. (2021), where the majority of their respondents had served for over five years but less than ten years. This supports the assumption of the present study that the length of service of personnel significantly contributes to their capability in handling and managing police records.

Attributes of Police Records Management

Table 5. Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes in terms of Records Creation

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Records are sufficient for audits.	4.57	0.679	Very Much Effective
2. Unneeded records and copies are kept to a minimum.	4.23	0.679	Very Much Effective
3. Official copies of records are identified.	4.63	0.490	Very Much Effective
4. Records are available for litigation.	4.57	0.626	Very Much Effective
5. Guidelines and other professional standards are used in records creation.	4.63	0.615	Very Much Effective
Overall Mean & SD	4.53	0.505	Very Much Effective

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 5 illustrates the respondent's perception of the attributes of police record management specifically in terms of records creation. The data indicates that police officers were rated as "very much effective" in all five categories related to records creation. This finding suggests that the police personnel responsible for record management demonstrated a strong understanding of the records creation process, recognizing that the creation or receipt of documents marks the beginning of the records management procedure.

This finding contradicts the results of Laguyo et al. (2020), where records creation was rated as moderately effective. This discrepancy implies the need for record management personnel to undergo programs that enhance their abilities in record creation.

Table 6. Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes in terms of Records Retention and Disposition

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Archival records are identified early in their life cycle.	4.50	0.682	Very Much Effective
2. Retention schedules are developed, adopted and used in the normal course of business	4.57	0.626	Very Much Effective
3. Records are systematically disposed of and routinely documented.	4.23	0.679	Very Much Effective
4. Electronic records are retained and disposed of according to retention schedules.	4.20	0.610	Very Much Effective
5. Plans are in place to ensure that electronic records continue to be accessible following the technology changes.	4.40	0.621	Very Much Effective
Overall Mean & SD	4.38	0.547	Very Much Effective

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 6 presents the profile of the police record management system regarding document retention and disposition in the surveyed police stations. The data indicates that respondents rated record retention and disposition as "very much effective" in all five items. Overall, the record managers demonstrated a high level of effectiveness in handling the retention and disposal of records. This suggests that the police record managers were knowledgeable about the regulations governing record keeping and disposal, and a retention schedule was implemented in the investigated police stations to determine the lifespan of records at each stage of the information life cycle.

This finding contradicts the results of Laguyo et al. (2020), where the mean score for records retention and disposition was interpreted as effective.

Table 7. Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes in terms of Records Storage and Maintenance

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Inactive records are stored off-site in an in-house or contracted records center.	4.23	0.817	Very Much Effective
2. Vaults and proper shelving are used for the most valuable records.	4.53	0.681	Very Much Effective
3. Microfilm masters, computer backups, and electronic data backup procedures are in place, routinely followed and stored off-site.	4.30	0.915	Very Much Effective
4. Disaster preparedness plans, fire prevention systems, adequate environmental controls and security rules and regulations are in place in storage areas.	4.50	0.731	Very Much Effective
5. Recording format standards are complied with.	4.55	0.736	Very Much Effective
Overall Mean & SD	4.42	0.660	Very Much Effective

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 7 presents the profile of records storage and maintenance in the analyzed Police Stations' record management system. The data indicates that respondents rated records storage and maintenance as "very much effective" across all five items. Overall, the respondents assessed the Police Stations as highly effective in records storage and maintenance, indicating that records were securely stored in clean and well-guarded areas. This finding suggests that the stations successfully implemented policies related to record keeping and upkeep.

This finding aligns with the study conducted by Laguyo et al. (2020), which also indicated a very high level of effectiveness in records storage and maintenance. It implies that police personnel received proper training in safeguarding and maintaining records.

Table 8. Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes in terms of Records Access and Retrieval

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Satisfactory filing and locator systems with documented policies and procedures.	4.47	0.776	Very Much Effective
2. Finding aids, such as indexes, are prepared and used.	4.50	0.861	Very Much Effective
3. Policies and procedures regarding access restrictions are developed and used.	4.57	0.728	Very Much Effective
4. Filing equipment is used appropriately.	4.57	0.728	Very Much Effective
5. Electronic database policies and procedures are developed and in use.	4.37	0.999	Very Much Effective
Overall Mean & SD	4.49	0.753	Very Much Effective

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Records access and retrieval refers to the availability of stored documents ready for access and ensures rapid recovery. Table 8 presents the records access and retrieval profile of the police records management system in the Police Stations included in the study. Respondents rated their police record sections as "very much effective" in accessing and retrieving documented information. The overall finding disclosed that the Police records management system of the Police Stations covered in the study was "very much effectively" managed by the Police records officers. It means that records in the stations were made accessible and could be retrieved when the need arose. It may also imply that records in the station were accessible and retrievable by the public.

The current study result was supported by the findings of Laguyo et al., (2020), in terms of records access and retrieval, the investigated police personnel were very much effective in doing so. This signifies that the personnel were highly effective in accessing and retrieving records.

Table 9. Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes in terms of Appropriate Use of Technology

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Recordkeeping requirements is taken into account in technology implementation.	4.40	1.070	Very Much Effective
2. PNP standards for acquiring and implementing technology are complied with.	4.37	0.964	Very Much Effective
3. Adequate technical support is available internally or via contract.	4.43	0.935	Very Much Effective

4. Formal electronic filing structures and policies for electronic recordkeeping are in place.	4.47	0.937	Very Much Effective
5. Adequate training for staff in the use of technology.	4.33	0.711	Very Much Effective
Overall Mean & SD	4.40	0.863	Very Much Effective

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 9 provides insights into the indicators of the "appropriate use of technology" in the study, focusing on cost-effectiveness, productivity, and efficiency. Respondents consistently rated all five indicators as "very much effective." This implies that the police stations effectively implemented technology that aligned with recordkeeping requirements, complied with Philippine National Police standards, provided adequate technical support, had formal electronic filing structures and policies, and offered sufficient training for staff in technology usage.

Overall, respondents rated their stations as highly effective in terms of the appropriate use of technology. This suggests that police stations embraced technological advancements, considering factors such as scale, labor, energy efficiency, environmental sustainability, and local control. It indicates that the stations viewed technology as a tool for intellectual, societal, and cultural advancement.

This finding contradicts the findings of Laguyo et al. (2020), where the results indicated a moderately effective rating for the appropriate use of technology. This suggests that police personnel in their study had a moderate familiarity with selecting the right technology for effective records management.

Table 10. Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes in terms of Archival Records

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Records reference use areas are available for the public.	4.10	0.923	Much Effective
2. Policies and procedures are in place for use of records by the public.	4.07	0.828	Much Effective
3. Information sharing with other agencies or organizations is done to develop and distribute finding aids to access to archival records is improved.	4.03	0.809	Much Effective
4. Records are used for exhibits and education.	4.03	1.033	Much Effective
5. The internet and marketing strategies are made available and are in place for public access to and actual use of records.	4.00	0.983	Much Effective
Overall Mean & SD	4.05	0.858	Much Effective

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Archival records are materials preserved for their valuable knowledge or as evidence of roles and responsibilities. They include papers, texts, images, videos, sound recordings, and more. Table 10 shows the archival records profile in the investigated Police Stations, with each indicator receiving a "much effective" rating. This indicates that the Police staff recognized the importance of preserving records for their enduring significance. The findings align with Laguyo et al.'s (2020) study, supporting the assumption that records should be preserved.

Table 11. Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes in terms of Records Management Program Integration

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Records management policies and procedures are in place and updated regularly.	4.50	0.731	Very Much Effective
2. Records policies and procedures and routinely and consistently communicated to the staff.	4.47	0.730	Very Much Effective
3. A disaster preparedness plan is in place and reviewed regularly.	4.40	0.855	Very Much Effective
4. A records management advisory council, officer and staff are appointed and active.	4.60	0.675	Very Much Effective
5. Staffs attends archives workshops, professional conferences, and other educational events.	4.20	0.761	Very Much Effective
Overall Mean & SD	4.43	0.671	Very Much Effective

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Program integration for records management involves combining various elements and coordinating multiple tasks. Table 11 presents the integration indicators for the records management program in the studied Police Stations. All indicators received a "very much effective" rating from respondents. Overall, the Police Stations obtained a "very much effective" rating for integrating their records management programs. This suggests that the police station's system for managing records provides clear directions and instructions for the administration and maintenance of public records. The records management program also trains officials and managers to ensure effective records management.

This finding is consistent with the results of Laguyo et al. (2020), where respondents also rated records management program integration as "very much effective."

Table 12. Summary of the Respondents' Perception Level of Police Record Management Attributes

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Records Creation	4.53	0.505	Very Much Effective

Records Retention and Disposition	4.38	0.547	Very Much Effective
Records Storage and Maintenance	4.42	0.660	Very Much Effective
Records Access and Retrieval	4.49	0.753	Very Much Effective
Appropriate Use of Technology	4.40	0.863	Very Much Effective
Archival Records	4.05	0.858	Much Effective
Records Management Program Integration	4.43	0.671	Very Much Effective
Grand Mean & SD	4.39	0.578	Very Much Effective

SD-Standard Deviation

Table 12 presents the summary profile of the police records management system in the investigated Police Stations. The respondents rated the system as "very much effective" in six indicators, including records creation, retention and disposition, storage and maintenance, access and retrieval, appropriate use of technology, and records management program integration. Archival records received a rating of "much effective." Overall, the record managers were highly effective in delivering the police records management system, indicating that the studied police stations implemented a strategic records management system to gain a competitive edge.

This finding contradicts the results of Laguyo et al. (2020) in terms of records creation, retention and disposal, and appropriate use of technology, which were interpreted as fairly effective. However, the results for records access and retrieval, storage and maintenance, and archival records were consistent with the findings of the present study.

Problems Encountered by Police Personnel in Managing Police Records

Table 13. Problems Encountered by Police Personnel in Managing Police Records

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Misplacing of documents, files, records and mails of all kinds such as letters memoranda and faxes.	1.73	1.112	Not Serious
2. Attaching of irrelevant documents and passing it to other police personnel.	1.73	1.172	Not Serious
3. Unable to determine what kind of file and documents they are handling.	1.63	1.066	Not Serious
4. Mishandling of the computers and other technology used for storing records.	1.59	0.907	Not Serious
5. Insufficient storage for files and records.	1.87	1.042	Less Serious
6. Time of finding the needed files.	1.80	1.064	Less Serious

7. Presence of outdated and unnecessary files.	1.77	0.971	Not Serious
8. Lost documents or unable to return the documents to the filing cabinet/storage.	1.80	1.064	Less Serious
9. Duplication of files that makes the police personnel confused of the records kept.	1.73	1.048	Not Serious
10. No record or uncoordinated transferring of a document from one personnel to another.	1.87	1.137	Less Serious
Overall Mean & SD	1.76	0.996	Not Serious

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 13 presents the issues faced by police staff in managing police records. The table indicates that six issues were not considered significant by the police records officers. These findings suggest that managing police records posed minimal challenges for law enforcement officers. It demonstrates that the officers responsible for handling documented information had the necessary knowledge and experience to maintain records securely. Additionally, it indicates that the studied Police Stations provided effective facilities for storing, retrieving, retaining, manipulating, archiving, and viewing law enforcement-related data, records, documents, or files.

This finding supports the results of Buen et al. (2017), where the overall mean score of 2.15 suggests that the encountered problems were not serious and did not significantly impact the capability of police personnel in handling and managing police records.

Factors Precipitating the Police Personnel Problems Encountered in Managing Police Records

Table 14. The Extent of the Factors Precipitating the Police Personnel Problems Encountered in Managing Police Records

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Interpretation
1. Insufficient knowledge of records' management	1.90	1.125	To a least extent
2. Lack of experience.	1.90	1.062	To a least extent
3. Personal matters affecting concentration and efficiency.	1.79	1.048	Not at all
4. Family issues	2.03	1.066	To a least extent
5. Financial problems	2.10	1.094	To a least extent
6. Performing multiple police functions such as patrolling, OPLAN Bakal, OPLAN Sita and etc.	3.07	1.337	To a moderate extent
7. Lack of English Proficiency.	2.20	0.997	To a least extent

8. Communication Barrier (dialects).	1.97	1.066	To a least extent
9. Ethnicity and race.	1.80	1.095	To a least extent
10. Changes in administration.	2.60	1.192	To a moderate extent
Overall Mean & SD	2.14	0.892	To a least extent

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 14 presents the causes contributing to the issues faced by police employees in managing police records. One item had minimal relevance, while two items were moderately influential. However, seven factors had the least impact on the problems encountered. Overall, these factors had minimal influence, indicating that police records managers had quality training and proficiency in record management. The results align with Buen et al.'s (2017) findings, suggesting that the identified factors do not significantly affect the proficiency of police officers in managing records.

Relationship Between the Attributes of Police Records Management and the Problems in Managing Police Records

Table 15. Test of Relationship Between the Attributes of Police Records Management and the Problems in Managing Records

Variables	Problems in Managing Records	
Records Creation	Correlation Coefficient	-0.390
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.033
	N	30
Records Retention and Disposition	Correlation Coefficient	-0.378
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.039
	N	30
Records Storage and Maintenance	Correlation Coefficient	-0.229
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.223
	N	30
Records Access and Retrieval	Correlation Coefficient	-0.528
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.003
	N	30
Appropriate Use of Technology	Correlation Coefficient	-0.169
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.371
	N	30
Archival Records	Correlation Coefficient	-0.234
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.214
	N	30
	Correlation Coefficient	-0.342

Records Management Program Integration	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.065
	N	30
Overall Attributes of Police Management	Correlation Coefficient	-0.339
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.067
	N	30

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 15 shows the relationship between police record management attributes and record management problems. It indicates that there was a significant relationship between accessing and retrieving records and issues with maintaining records, albeit not very strong. Additionally, a moderate and significant correlation was found between issues with managing police records and records creation, retention, and disposal. However, overall, there was no significant relationship between police record management attributes and record management problems. This supports the findings of Muhammad et al. (2020) that the attributes of records management were not correlated with the problems in police records management.

Relationship Between the Attributes of Police Records Management and the Factors Precipitating the Problems in Managing Records

Table 16. Test of Relationship Between the Attributes of Police Records Management and the Factors Precipitating the Problems in Managing Records

Variables	Factors Precipitating the Problems in Managing Records	
Records Creation	Correlation Coefficient	-0.537
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.002
	N	30
Records Retention and Disposition	Correlation Coefficient	-0.438
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.016
	N	30
Records Storage and Maintenance	Correlation Coefficient	-0.322
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.083
	N	30
Records Access and Retrieval	Correlation Coefficient	-0.578
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.001
	N	30
Appropriate Use of Technology	Correlation Coefficient	-0.371
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.043
	N	30
Archival Records	Correlation Coefficient	-0.329

		Sig.(2-tailed)	0.076
		N	30
Records Management Program Integration		Correlation Coefficient	-0.441
		Sig.(2-tailed)	0.015
		N	30
Overall Attributes of Police Records Management		Correlation Coefficient	-0.446
		Sig.(2-tailed)	0.013
		N	30

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 16 examines the relationship between police record management attributes and the causes of record management issues. It indicates a strong correlation between records generation, accessing, and retrieval, and the causes of problems in managing records. There is also a moderate correlation between records retention and disposition, appropriate use of technology, and program integration, and the factors causing record management issues. Overall, there is a moderate correlation between police record management attributes and the causes of these issues. These findings align with the results of Muhammad et al. (2020) that highlight the positive correlation between police records management attributes and the problems associated with record management.

Results and Discussion

The study examined various aspects of police record management and the issues faced by police personnel. The findings revealed a diverse profile of respondents, with a majority of male officers and a significant portion in the middle age group. Perceived attributes of police record management were rated as "very much effective." The problems encountered in managing police records were not perceived as serious, and factors such as performing multiple functions and changes in administration had moderate-level impact. However, there was no significant relationship between record management attributes and problems. The findings highlight the need for effective record management practices and continuous training and support in law enforcement agencies. Future research can focus on strategies to enhance record management processes.

Conclusion

The researchers concluded that factors causing the problems in processing police records contributed "to the least extent" to the problems that police personnel managing police records encountered. It is reasonable to presume that police records administrators had adequate police training. Moreover, study revealed that there was a close relationship between police record management attributes and the factors that contributed to record management difficulties. The link between the two variables was likewise somewhat significant. It means that the police records officers who managed their records well faced the factors most likely to cause issues with record management to a lesser extent.

It is recommended that the Philippine National Police administration shall conduct retraining programs and activities that allows those in-charge in records management to attain necessary skills that may enhance their efficacy in doing their job. It is recommended further to have an annual assessment among personnel in-charge in record management to ensure that they equipped knowledge in addressing problems that may arise in the course of record management.

References

- Bakare, A. A., Abioye, A., & Issa, A. O. (2016). *An Assessment of Records Management Practice in Selected Local Government Councils in Ogun State, Nigeria*. *Journal of Information Science Theory and Practice*, 4(1), 49-64. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1633/JIST>.
- Basilio, R. D., Cueto, M. M., Dumas, E. M., Ortega, M. J., Zapata, J. D., & Bautista, M. L. (n.d). *Job Satisfaction Levels of PNP Employees in a Provincial City*. *College of the Criminology Research Journal*, 8. Retrieved from <https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/CRIM-2017-002.pdf>
- Cappitelli, P. (2018). *5 of the biggest issues facing law enforcement in 2019*. Retrieved from <https://www.police1.com/2018-review/articles/5-of-the-biggest-issues-facing-law-...enforcement-in-2019-Nfo4Fin1vBoTwFJS/>.
- Chaiwuttisak, P. (2019). *Factors Affecting Efficiency of Police Stations in Metropolitan Police Division 3. ICoMS'19: Proceedings of the 2019 2nd International Conference on Mathematics and Statistics*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3343485.3343488>.
- Chokprachakchat, S. (2011). *Guidelines for the Royal Thai police's human resource management*. The Secretariat of the Senate, Bangkok, Thailand (2011).
- Chokprajakchat, S., Techagaisiyavanit, W., Kuanliang, A., & Sumretphol, N. (n.d.). *Practices in Violent Crime Reduction through Thailand's Experience*. *Journal of Applied Security Research*, 16, 370 - 389.
- Cunningham, M. (2021). *Police Records Management Systems vs. Case Management: What's the Difference?* Retrieved from <https://www.shotspotter.com/blog/police-records-management-systems-vs-case-management-whats-the-difference/>.
- Eduardo, J. P., & Gabriel, A. G. (2017). *Assessing the leadership skills of the chiefs of police in the towns of Nueva Ecija, Philippines: A dichotomy between managerial competence and decision-making ability*. *Open Journal of Leadership*, 6(4), 142-159.
- FBI. (1984). *Law Enforcement Records Management System*. FBI Law Enforcement Bulletin. Retrieved from file:///C:/Users/RAC/Downloads/DECEMBER%201987%20(3).pdf
- Gomes N., T., Lucas de Souza, E. C., & Adaid-Castro, B. G. (2020). *Professional competences scale for police officers: evidence of psychometric adequacy*. *RAP: Revista Brasileira de Administração Pública*, 54.
- Güss, C. D., Tuason, M. T., & Devine, A. (2020). *Problems With Police Reports as Data Sources: A Researchers' Perspective*. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. .
- Laguyo, J., & Caelian, M. (2020). *Police Operational Competence and Performance of Graduates of Regional Training Center*. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v3i2.177>
- Lokesh, L., Patra, S., & Venkatesan, S. (2016). *Job satisfaction among police personnel: a socio-demographic study*. *Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 4(5), 56-62.
- Muhammad, M., Yusha'u, A., Inuwa, I., & Usman, M. (2020). *Statistical analysis on public evaluation performance of police: A case study of yelwa division*. *International journal of applied research*, 6, 159-162.

Ngoepe, M. (2014). *The role of records management as a tool to identify risks in the public sector in South Africa*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271302831_The_role_of_records_management_as_a_tool_to_identify_risks_in_the_public_.

Ridener, J. (2009). *A Concise History of Archival Theory*. Duluth, MN: Litwin Books.

Saraih, U., Kalaranjan, Y., Ahmad, N., & Samah, I. (2021). *The presence of satisfaction among the royal Malaysian police: Empirical investigation related to human resource practices*. PROCEEDINGS OF GREEN DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE 2020.

Schaveling, J., Blaauw, S., & van Montfort, K. (2017). *Predictors of group performance in a police criminal investigation department: the role of gender homogeneity, leadership and team characteristics*. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology*, 32(4), 358-368.

Sulaiman, A., Hamsan, H., Yero, A., & Lawrence, J. (2021). *Police Officer's Commitment towards Community Policing in Malaysia: Instruments Development and Validation*. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*.

Tembur, A. (2017). *Factors affecting job performance in national police service. A case study of nairobi area county*. School of management and leadership. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/157498203.pdf>

Tengpongsthorn, W. (2017). *Factors affecting the effectiveness of police performance in Metropolitan Police Bureau*. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences*, 38(1), 39-44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kjss.2016.07.001>.

Varano, S., Cancino, J., Glass, J., & Enriquez, R. (2007). *Police information systems*. In *Policing 2020*, edited by J. Schafer. Washington, DC: Federal Bureau of Investigations.

WorldBank. (2006). *Why records management? Records management as a key support for effectiveness*. Retrieved from . .

Publisher's Note: DWIJMH stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

© 2023 by the authors. Licensee DWIJMH. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Divine Word International Journal of Management and Humanities. DWIJMH is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.